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Minimum tillage—an alternative preplanting technology to accelerate planting time and achieve optimal weed control in irrigated lowland rice

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Rice is the most important staple food in West Java, where it provides 50–70% of total calorie intake (Suryana and Budianto 1998). More than 90% of the rice supply in West Java comes from 0.9 million ha of irrigated lowland. However, productivity growth may be difficult to sustain because of limited tractor availability and improper water distribution. This has led to improper land preparation, nonuniform rice growth, increasing pest and weed populations, and yield loss during harvest. Such conditions have made minimum tillage with the use of herbicide, such as paraquat, much more viable. Research has shown that minimum tillage reduces costs in both direct-seeded and transplanted rice because of less labor cost for hand weeding and land preparation. Minimum tillage is viable in irrigated systems if cost-effective herbicides are used to control weeds (Puslitbangtan 1996).

To assess the performance of minimum tillage in accelerating planting time and achieving optimal weed control, two field experiments were conducted in farmers' fields during the wet season from October 2001 to February 2002 under irrigated conditions in the Subang District, West Java, Indonesia. The first experiment was conducted in large plots of 5 ha with and without minimum tillage and involving 7 cooperating and 10 noncooperating farmers, respectively. The farmers were consid-

ered as replications. Cooperating farmers implemented minimum tillage with the use of paraquat 10 and 8 d before transplanting (DBT) at 400 and 200 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively, followed by rototilling of the soil once at 3 DBT. Noncooperating farmers implemented existing farmers' practices (i.e., intensive tillage, which consists of plowing, harrowing, and rototilling before planting, followed by the application of triasulfuron 20% [5 g ai ha⁻¹] and 2,4-D [360 g ai ha⁻¹] 14–21 d after transplanting [DAT] as a weed control).

The second experiment (superimposed trial) involved six treatments in smaller plots of 30 m²: intensive tillage + no weed-

ing (T₁); intensive tillage + hand weeding twice at 21 and 45 DAT (T₂); intensive tillage + mixture of 2,4-D natrium (15 g ai ha⁻¹) and 2,4-D (360 g ai ha⁻¹) at 14 DAT (T₃); intensive tillage + mixture of triasulfuron (360 g ai ha⁻¹) and 2,4-D (360 g ai ha⁻¹) at 14 DAT (T₄); minimum tillage + paraquat applied 10 and 8 DBT at 400 and 200 g ai ha⁻¹, respectively (T₅); and minimum tillage + hand weeding at 21 DAT (T₆). These treatments were tested in a randomized complete block design with five replications. Observations on weed parameters were collected from 12 1-m² quadrats in opposite diagonals of each plot.

Results from smaller plots (Table 1) showed no significant

Table 1. Influence of tillage system and method of weed control on weed population, yield, and economics of lowland irrigated rice.

Tillage system and weed control method ^a	Weed population at 40 DAT ^b (g m ⁻²)			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Net income ^c (Rp 000 ha ⁻¹)	Revenue-cost ratio
	Grass	Sedge	Broadleaf			
<i>Intensive tillage</i>						
T ₁ = no weeding	3.2 a ²	0.0	14.8 a	6.5 ns	5,775	1.9
T ₂ = hand-weeded twice at 21 and 45 DAT	1.3 b	0.0	0.1 c	6.6	5,726	1.8
T ₃ = 2,4-D natrium (15 g ai ha ⁻¹) + 2,4-D (360 g ai ha ⁻¹) at 14 DAT	0.3 c	0.0	0.4 c	6.1	5,102	1.7
T ₄ = triasulfuron (360 ai ha ⁻¹) + 2,4-D (360 g ai ha ⁻¹) at 14 DAT	1.3 b	0.0	2.8 b	6.5	5,669	1.8
<i>Minimum tillage</i>						
T ₅ = no weeding	1.4 b	0.0	3.7 ab	6.4	6,374	2.8
T ₆ = hand weeded once at 21 DAT	0.0 c	0.0	0.0 c	6.8	6,791	2.9
CV	18.3	0.0	16.5	12.9		

^aNumbers in a column followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at 5% by Duncan's multiple range test; ns = not significant. ^bDAT = days after transplanting; minimum tillage: paraquat at 400 and 200 g ai ha⁻¹ 10 and 8 d before transplanting, respectively. ^cUS\$1 = Rp 10,000.

Table 2. Influence of tillage system on weed population and rice yield.

Tillage system	Weed population at 40 DAT ^a (g m ⁻²)			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
	Broadleaf	Sedge	Grass	
<i>Before application</i>				
Minimum tillage	146.1	29.5	97.1	nr ^b
Intensive tillage	164.5	43.8	101.8	nr
<i>40 DAT</i>				
Minimum tillage	0.7	0.0	1.5	5.5
Intensive tillage	1.5	0.0	0.2	5.3

^aDAT = days after transplanting. ^bnr = not recorded.

Table 3. Effect of tillage system on time of land preparation and economics of lowland irrigated rice.

Parameter	Tillage system		Difference (MT - IT)
	Intensive tillage (IT)	Minimum tillage (MT)	
<i>Land preparation</i>			
Time (h ha ⁻¹)	12.8	3.8	-9.0
Value (Rp 000 ha ⁻¹) ^a	250.0	62.2	-187.8
Herbicide application (Rp 000 ha ⁻¹)	623.5	37.4	-586.1
Net income (Rp 000 ha ⁻¹)	4,611.8	4,894.7	282.9
R/C ^b	1.7	1.9	0.2
MBCR ^c	1.7	2.8	1.1

^aUS\$1 = Rp 10,000. ^bR/C = revenue-cost ratio. ^cMBCR = marginal benefit-cost ratio.

differences in weed population and grain yield between minimum and intensive tillage with and without various additional weed control methods, including the use of herbicide for intensive tillage. However, for both minimum tillage treatments, with and without an additional hand weeding, the land preparation and weed control costs were less than for intensive tillage; the reduced labor cost translated into an increase in income and revenue-cost ratio. The net income

and revenue-cost ratio were the highest for minimum tillage with an additional hand weeding at 21 DAT, closely followed by minimum tillage without hand weeding.

The experiment in bigger plots proved the adaptability of minimum tillage in farmers' fields. Results clearly showed that minimum tillage is a low-cost practice that facilitates faster planting while maintaining the same levels of grain yield and weed control as with intensive

tillage (Table 2). Planting time was accelerated in minimum tillage systems (from 3.8 h ha⁻¹) because of a 400% reduction in the time needed for land preparation when compared with intensive tillage systems (12.8 h ha⁻¹) (Table 3). This dramatic savings in time and labor costs makes paraquat use both economically and socially attractive. Suyamto et al (1991) reported similar benefits of minimum tillage using paraquat over intensive tillage. Such advantages are expected to make minimum tillage widely adaptable in West Java, Indonesia, where land preparation is mainly done by small tractors and where tractor availability is limited.

References

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